

PATHWAYS

Pathways wave #1 Codebook

Variable name	Variable label	Original questions / answers	Answer value	Survey logic
Pre-interview information				
pre_supervisor_c3	Supervisor name	Supervisor name		
		Supervisor name 1	1	
		Supervisor name 2	2	
		Supervisor name 3	3	
pre_enumerator_c23	Enumerator name	Enumerator name		
		Name 1	1	
		Name 2	2	
		Name 3	3	
		Name 4	4	
		Name 5	5	
		Name 6	6	
		Name 7	7	
		Name 8	8	
		Name 9	9	
		Name 10	10	
		Name 11	11	
		Name 12	12	
		Name 13	13	
		Name 14	14	
		Name 15	15	
		Name 16	16	
		Name 17	17	
		Name 18	18	
		Name 19	19	
		Name 20	20	
		Name 21	21	
		Name 22	22	
		Name 23	23	
pre_locality_c3	Locality	Locality name		
		Ziguinchor	1	
		Kolda	2	
		Bagadadgi (villages	3	
pre_zigzone_c5	Ziguinchor zone	Zone in Ziguinchor		
		zone 1	1	
		zone 2	2	
		zone 3	3	

		zone 4	4	
		zone 5	5	
pre_quartier_c82	Locality quartier	Quartier in each locality		
		Ziguinchor-Soucoupapaye	1	
		Ziguinchor-Boucotte Sud	2	
		Ziguinchor-Lyndiane	3	
		Ziguinchor-Coboda	4	
		Ziguinchor-Colobane	5	
		Ziguinchor-Djiringho	6	
		Ziguinchor-Lyndiane 1	7	
		Ziguinchor-Colobane Fass	8	
		Ziguinchor-Niafoulène	9	
		Ziguinchor-Belfort	10	
		Ziguinchor-Boudody Escale	11	
		Ziguinchor-Sanathiaba Ouest	12	
		Ziguinchor-Goumel	13	
		Ziguinchor-Diéfaye	14	
		Ziguinchor-Kandé Sibink	15	
		Ziguinchor-Kandé Alassane	16	
		Ziguinchor-Sanathiaba Est	17	
		Ziguinchor-Djibok	18	
		Ziguinchor-Tilène	19	
		Ziguinchor-Kandialang Est	20	
		Ziguinchor-Kandialang Ouest	21	
		Ziguinchor-Alwar	22	
		Ziguinchor-Néma1	23	
		Ziguinchor-Diabir	24	
		Ziguinchor-Kansaoudy	25	
		Ziguinchor-Kénia	26	
		Ziguinchor-Castor	27	
		Ziguinchor-Némaz	28	
		Ziguinchor-Boucotte Centre	29	
		Ziguinchor-Boucotte Est	30	
		Ziguinchor-Boucotte ouest	31	
		Ziguinchor-Boucotte Nord	32	
		Ziguinchor-Cobitène	33	
		Ziguinchor-Peyrissac	34	
		Ziguinchor-Kadior	35	
		Kolda-Sikilo	36	
		Kolda-Doumassou	37	
		Kolda-Bel Air	38	
		Kolda-Gadapara	39	
		Kolda-Saré Kemo	40	
		Kolda-Sinthiang Idrissa	41	
		Kolda-Bouna Kane	42	
		Kolda-Sinthiang Tountouroung	43	
		Kolda-Bantanguel	44	
		Kolda-Saré Moussa	45	

		Kolda-Hilélé	46	
		Kolda-Escale	47	
		Kolda-NDIOBÈNE	48	
		Kolda-Hafia	49	
		Kolda-Usine Coton	50	
		Kolda-Champs de tirs	51	
		Kolda-Sikilo-Est	52	
		Kolda-Sikilo-Ouest	53	
		Bagadadji-Sikilo-Nord	54	
		Bagadadji-Sikilo-Trypano	55	
		Bagadadji-Sikilo-Médina Chérif	56	
		Bagadadji-Doumassou-Plateau	57	
		Bagadadji-Doumassou-Zone Élevage	58	
		Bagadadji-Bouna Kane-Plateau	59	
		Bagadadji-Bouna Kane-Zone élevage	60	
		Bagadadji-Missirah Samba	61	
		Niamadio	62	
		Bagadadji-Kampissa	62	
		Bagadadji-Sinthiang Dembarou Couro	63	
		Bagadadji-Missirah Mamadou	64	
		Bagadadji-Sare Sara	65	
		Bagadadji-Salamata	66	
		Bagadadji-Medina Aliou Samba	67	
		Bagadadji-linkerinto	68	
		Bagadadji-sare bocar	69	
		Bagadadji-sare sandiong	70	
		Bagadadji-tanbandinto	71	
		Bagadadji-medina dalatou	72	
		Bagadadji-Sinthiang Elhadji Saliou (Elh hadji saliou)	73	
		Bagadadji-Iliyawo mamadou seydou	74	
		Bagadadji-sinthiang souma	75	
		Bagadadji-medina fode	76	
		Bagadadji-missirah kamarang	77	
		Bagadadji-Medina Seydou Ba	78	
		Bagadadji-Manthieng kany	79	
		Bagadadji-Sare Sonia	80	
		Bagadadji-Sare Lountang	81	
		Bagadadji-Sare Coly	82	
Module a: Basic information & Household composition				
a1_name_t	Name	Please repeat your full name		
		Open answer	#	
a2_age_n	Age	What is your age?		
		Open answer	#	
a3_gender_c3	Gender	What is your gender?		
		Male	1	
		Female	2	

		Other (nonbinary, transgender, for example)	3	
		Prefer not to say	4	
a4_lang_LANG_d		Please tell me the languages in which you feel comfortable to have a conversation?		
		Arabic	1	
		Balanta-Ganja	2	
		Diola Casa	3	
		Diola Boulouf	4	
		Dutch	5	
		English	6	
		French	7	
		German	8	
		Italian	9	
		Jola-Fonyi	10	
		Mandinka	11	
		Mandjak	12	
		Mankanya	13	
		Noon (Serer-Noon)	14	
		Pulaar	15	
		Serer	16	
		Soninke	17	
		Spanish	18	
		Wolof	19	
		Other, please specify	20	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a5_langoth_t		Please specify		if a4_lang_LANG_d=18
		Open answer	s	
a6_grew1_c6	Growing up location	Where did you mainly grew up as a child?		
		Here, in the same neighbourhood	1	
		Here in [LOCATION], but another neighbourhood	2	
		Elsewhere in Casamance	3	
		Elsewhere in Senegal	4	
		In another country in Africa	5	
		In another country outside of Africa	6	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a7_grew2_c3	Arrival to location	When did you move to this neighbourhood?		if a6_grew1_c6=
		Less than a year ago	1	
		Between 1 and 5 years ago	2	
		More than 5 years ago	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

a8_parents	Lives with parents	Do you live with your parents?		
		No	0	
		Only with my father	1	
		Only with my mother	2	
		Yes, with both parents	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a9_partner	Partnership status	Are you married? or do you have a fiancée, fiancé, partner, or girl/boyfriend?		
		No	0	
		Yes, married	1	
		Yes, other type of partner	2	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a10_wivenum	# of wives	How many wives do you have?		if a9_partner_c3 =1 and a3_gender_c3
		Open answer	#	
a11_cowivenum	# of co-wives	How many co-wives do you have?		if a9_partner_c3 =1 and a3_gender_c3 =0
		Open answer	#	
a12_wivesloc	# of wives living with respondent	and from those, how many live with you?		if a10_wivenum _n>1 or a11_cowivenu m_n>1
		Open answer	#	
a13_ptnloc	Partner location	Where does your partner (main wife) live?		if partner==1 or 2 & a12_wivesloc_ n=0
		With the respondent	1	
		Elsewhere in [LOCATION]	2	
		Elsewhere in Senegal	3	
		In another country	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a14_parent	Is parent	Do you have any children?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a15_chdnu	# of children	How many?		if a14_parent_d
		Open answer	#	
a16_chdnuhh	# of children living with respondent	and from those, how many live with you?		if a14_parent_d
		Open answer	#	

a17_sibnum_n	# of (half) siblings	How many siblings (including half-siblings) do you have?		
		Open answer	#	
a18_sibloc_n	# of (half) siblings living with respondent	and from those, how many live with you?		if a17_sibnum_n >0
		Open answer	#	
a19_hhnum_n	# of other people living with respondent	Other than your children and siblings, how many other people live in your household?		
		Open answer	#	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a20_hheld_n	# of elderly living with respondent	And how many of them are elderly (Aged above 65 years		
		Open answer	#	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a21_hhsize_n	Total number of people living in hh	So, there are (number) people living in this household, correct?		
		Open answer	#	
a22_famfinsup_n	# of relatives in need of respondent's financial care	Now thinking on your relatives that live with you or in another house. Of these, how many need your financial care?		
		Open answer	#	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a23_famcarsup_n	# of relatives of relatives in need of respondent's (non financial) care	And how many need other types of care that would require your presence?		
		Open answer	#	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a24_famsupneed_d	Respondent is the only person that can provide this care	Would you say that you are the only person that could provide this care?		if a22_famfinsup_n >0 or a23_famcarsup_n >0
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a25_famsuptot_c4	Level of care that respondent can (actually) provide	How much of the care they need are you able to provide?		if a22_famfinsup_n >0 or a23_famcarsup_n >0
		None of it	1	
		Some of it	2	
		Most of it	3	
		All of it	4	
		Don't know	.a	

		Refuse to answer	.b	
a26_famsupbur_c2	Feels overburdened by these needs of care	Do you feel overburdened by these needs for your care, or not so much?		if a22_famfinsup_n>0 or a23_famcarsu p n>0
		Feels overburdened	1	
		Not so much	2	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a27_hhmmabr_n	# of hh members abroad	How many members from this household live in another		
		number	#	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a28_hhmmabr_COUNTRY_d		And where do they live?		if a27_hhmmabr_n>0
		Multiple selection country list	List	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a29_relabr_n	# of other relatives abroad	And how many other relatives or friends live in another		
		0	0	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a30_relabr_COUNTRY_d		And where do they live?		if a29_relabr_n>
		Multiple selection country list	List	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a31_tntcon_d	Contact with relatives or hh members abroad	And have you talked with, or exchanged messages with any of them while abroad during the past year?		if a27_hhmmabr_n>0 or a29_relabr_n>
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a32_remit_d	Household received remittances over the past year	Has anyone who lives abroad sent money to you or anyone in your household during the past year?		if a27_hhmmabr_n>0 or a29_relabr_n>
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
a33_remitval_c3	Importance of remittances	How important is this money for supporting your household?		if a32_remit_d=1
		Very important	1	
		Somewhat important	2	
		Not so important	3	
		Don't know	.a	

		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module b: life goals				
b1_firstlg_c5 // b2_secondlg_c5	First life goal // Second life goal	Everyone has long-term goals in life. These are the things that you hope to accomplish over the course of your life. In this section, we will ask you a few questions about your life goals. Below you can see 5 examples of life goals. From this list, please select which would be your 2 main life goals in order of relevance. If one of your life goals is not listed in the answers provided, please use		
		To have enough money to buy everything I need and want	1	
		To be admired/well regarded by many people	2	
		To have deep enduring relationships with friends and family	3	
		To help and/or support people in my local community	4	
		Other, please specify	5	
b1_firstlgoth_t // b2_secondlgoth_t	First life goal other // Second life goal other	Please specify		
		Open answer	s	
b3_firstlghere_d // b4_secondlghere_d	Thinks can achieve first goal here // Thinks can achieve second goal here	Do you think you will be able to attain this goal here in [LOCATION]?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
b5_firstlgwhere_c3 // b6_secondlgwhere_c3	Where first goal could be achieved // Where second goal could be achieved	Where do you think achieving your goal would be more feasible?		if b3_firstlghere_d // b4_secondlghere_d=0
		Elsewhere in Senegal	1	
		Elsewhere in West Africa	2	
		Outside of West Africa	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
b7_firstlgprefer_c4 // b8_secondlgprefer_c4	Preferred location to achieve first goal // Preferred location to achieve	And, if you could choose, where would you want to achieve your main life goals?		
		Here, in [LOCATION]	1	
		Elsewhere in Senegal	2	
		Elsewhere in West Africa	3	
		Outside of West Africa	4	

		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module c: Subjective well being				
c1_lifesat_c10	General life satisfaction	Now, I will ask you some questions about your life, standard of living and health. For all the questions we will use the same scale in this card where 0 represents "Not satisfied at all" and 10 represents "Completely satisfied". All things considered, how satisfied are		
		Not satisfied at all	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Completely satisfied	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c2_phyhealthsat_c10	Physical health satisfaction	How satisfied are you with your physical health?		
		Not satisfied at all	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Completely satisfied	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c3_menhealthsat_c10	Mental health satisfaction	How satisfied are you with your mental health?		
		Not satisfied at all	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Completely satisfied	10	

		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c4_goalsat_c10	Achievement satisfaction	How satisfied are you with what you are achieving in life?		
		Not satisfied at all	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Completely satisfied	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c5_safesat_c10	Safety satisfaction	How satisfied are you with how safe you feel?		
		Not satisfied at all	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Completely satisfied	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c6_commsat_c10	Community involvement satisfaction	How satisfied are you with feeling part of your community?		
		Not satisfied at all	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Completely satisfied	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c7_jobsat_c10	Job satisfaction	How satisfied are you with your (main) job?		
		Not satisfied at all	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	

		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Completely satisfied	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c8_cheer_c6	<i>Feels cheerful and in good spirits</i>	Please indicate for each of the following five statements which is closest to how you have been feeling over the past two weeks. I have felt cheerful and in good spirits		
		At no time	0	
		Some of the time	1	
		Less than half the time	2	
		More than half the time	3	
		Most of the time	4	
		All of the time	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c9_relax_c6	<i>Feels calm and relaxed</i>	I have felt calm and relaxed		
		At no time	0	
		Some of the time	1	
		Less than half the time	2	
		More than half the time	3	
		Most of the time	4	
		All of the time	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c10_active_c6	<i>Feels active and vigorous</i>	I have felt active and vigorous		
		At no time	0	
		Some of the time	1	
		Less than half the time	2	
		More than half the time	3	
		Most of the time	4	
		All of the time	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c11_fresh_c6	<i>Feels fresh and rested</i>	I woke up feeling fresh and rested		
		At no time	0	
		Some of the time	1	
		Less than half the time	2	
		More than half the time	3	
		Most of the time	4	
		All of the time	5	

		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c12_fullfilled_c6	<i>Feels fulfilled</i>	My daily life has been filled with things that interest me		
		At no time	0	
		Some of the time	1	
		Less than half the time	2	
		More than half the time	3	
		Most of the time	4	
		All of the time	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c13_nervous_c4	<i>Feels nervous, anxious or on edge</i>	Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by feeling nervous, anxious or on edge?		
		Not at all	1	
		Several days	2	
		More than half the days	3	
		Nearly every day	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c14_worried_c4	<i>Feels not being able to stop or control worrying</i>	And have you not being able to stop or control worrying?		
		Not at all	1	
		Several days	2	
		More than half the days	3	
		Nearly every day	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c15_self_c10	<i>Feels very positive about themselves</i>	Now, once again, I will read you out loud several statements about possible ways you might feel. For all the following statements please tell me your level of agreement in a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 represents "Disagree completely" and 10 represents "Agree completely". In general,		
		Disagree completely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Agree completely	10	

		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c16_futureprosp_c10	<i>Feels satisfied with their future prospects</i>	I am satisfied with my future prospects		
		Disagree completely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Agree completely	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c17_optimistic_c10	<i>Is always optimistic about</i>	I'm always optimistic about my future		
		Disagree completely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Agree completely	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c18_volition_c10	<i>Is free to decide how to live their</i>	I am free to decide for myself how to live my life		
		Disagree completely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Agree completely	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

c19_accomplished_c10	Most days gets a sense of accomplishment	Most days I get a sense of accomplishment from what I do		
		Disagree completely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Agree completely	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c20_changeaverse_c10	Takes long time to get back to normal when things go wrong	When things go wrong in my life it generally takes me a long time to get back to normal		
		Disagree completely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Agree completely	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
c21_related_c10	Feels connected to other people important to them	I feel close and connected with other people who are important to me. (Relatedness)		
		Disagree completely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Agree completely	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

c22_cantril_c10	Cantril ladder	Finally, now please imagine a ladder, with steps numbered from 0 at the bottom to 10 at the top. The top of the ladder represents the best possible life for you, and the bottom of the ladder represents the worst possible life for you. On which step of the ladder would you say you personally feel you stand at this time?"		
		Worst possible life 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 Best possible life Don't know Refuse to answer	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 .a .b	
Module d: Migration aspirations and related concepts				
d1_migpast_c3	Has lived in another country for at least one year	Have you ever lived in another country for at least one year?		
		No Yes, less than 5 years ago Yes, more than 5 years ago Don't know Refuse to answer	0 1 2 .a .b	
d2_ctyabr_COUNTRY_d		In which country, or countries?		
		List of countries		
d3_migpref_c2	Preference to stay or to migrate	And, if you could choose, would you like to go and live in another country some time during the next five years, or would you prefer to stay in		
		Stay in Senegal Go to another country Don't know / Don't have a strong preference Refuse to answer	0 1 .a .b	
d4_migprefrank_c10	Preferences ranking	Now please look at this card. If you could rank your preferences on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means you staying in Senegal and 10 means going to another country for some time in the next five years. where would		

		Stay in Senegal	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Go to another country	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d5_migprefsen_c4	Staying preference location	Where in Senegal would you prefer to be living in the following five years?		if d3_migpref_c2=1
		here, in the same neighbourhood	1	
		Here in [LOCATION], but another neighbourhood	2	
		In Dakar	3	
		Elsewhere in Senegal	4	
		Don't know / Don't have a strong preference	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d6_pref_COUNTRY_d		To which countries would you prefer to go?		if d3_migpref_c2=2
		List of countries		
d7_migprefcty2_c27	Preferred destination	If you were to chose one country out of the list you just mentioned, which one would be your preferred destination?		if d3_migpref_c2=2
		List of countries (single selection)		
		Don't know / Don't have a strong preference		
		Refuse to answer		
d8_migconswa_d	Has considered migration within WA	And have you seriously considered leaving Senegal to live in another country within		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d9_migconsyrwa_d	Has considered migration within WA (last year)	Have you considered it during the past year?		if d8_migconswa_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

d10_migconsoutwa_d	Has considered migration outside WA	And have you seriously considered leaving Senegal to live in another country outside of West Africa?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d11_migconsyroutwa_d	Has considered migration outside WA (last year)	Have you considered it during the past year?		if migconsoutwa=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d12_persisoutwa_c4	Persistence of aspiration outside WA	You have mentioned that you would like to go and live in another country some time during the next five years, for how long have you been wanting to go to a country outside of West Africa?		if migpref=1 & migprefcty=country outside west africa
		Only recently, this month	1	
		Only recently, this year	2	
		For more than a year but less than 5 years	3	
		For more than 5 years	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d13_persisinwa_c4	Persistence of aspiration within WA	You have mentioned that you would like to go and live in another country some time during the next five years, for how long have you been wanting to go to a country within West Africa?		if if d3_migpref_c2=2
		Only recently, this month	1	
		Only recently, this year	2	
		For more than a year but less than 5 years	3	
		For more than 5 years	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d14_returnasp_c2	Settle or return aspiration	If you were to live in your preferred destination, would you want to settle and establish a life there, or to move back to Senegal after some time?		if d3_migpref_c2=2
		Settle and establish life there	0	
		Move back after some time	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

d15_purpose1_c7	Purpose for migration aspiration	And, which would be the main purpose for this travel?		if d3_migpref_c2=2
		To work and earn money mainly for myself	1	
		To work and earn money to sustain family in Senegal	2	
		Education abroad	3	
		To gain valuable personal experiences	4	
		To reunite with partner, parents or children	5	
		To feel safer	6	
		Other, please specify	7	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d16_purpose10th_t	Other purpose for migration	Please specify		
		Open answer		
d17_condition1_d	Would still prefer to migrate even if had an income and could live comfortably i	If you had an income and could live comfortably here, would you still prefer to live in another country or would you prefer to stay?		if d15_purpose1_c7=1 or 2
		Live here	0	
		Live in another country	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d18_condition2_d	Would still prefer to migrate even if could get the education wishes in Senegal	If you could get the education you wish here in Senegal, would you still prefer to live in another country or would you prefer to stay?		if d15_purpose1_c7=3
		Live here	0	
		Live in another country	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d19_condition3_d	Would still prefer to migrate even if would feel safer in location	If you would feel safer here, would you still prefer to live in another country or would you prefer to stay?		if d15_purpose1_c7=6
		Live here	0	
		Live in another country	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d20_lklhdwa_c10	Likelihood of migrating within WA in next 5 years	In a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 denotes very unlikely and 10 very likely, how likely do you think it is that you would go to live in another country within west Africa during the next 5		
		Very unlikely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	

		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Very likely	10	
d21_iklhoutwa_c10	Likelihood of migrating outside WA in next 5 years	In a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 denotes very unlikely and 10 very likely, how likely is it that you would go to live outside of West Africa during the next 5		
		Very unlikely	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Very likely	10	
d22_migready_d	Would migrate outside WA if given ticket and visa	If you could get a ticket and visa to go live in a country outside of West Africa of your choice, would you go or would you stay in Senegal?		
		Stay	0	
		Go to another country	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d23_migreadymn_d	Would migrate (within a month) outside WA if given ticket and visa	Would you be willing to go (leave) within a month?		if d22_migready_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d24_press_d	Has been urged to migrate outside WA	Has anyone urged you to go to live outside of West Africa?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d25_presswho_WHO_d		Who did urge you? (Multiple response)		if d24_press_d=1
		Spouse/partner, ex-partner	1	
		Children	2	

		Mother	3	
		Father	4	
		Siblings	5	
		Cousins	6	
		Other relatives	7	
		Friends	8	
		Religious leader	9	
		Other	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
d26_pressure_d	Thinks pressure has influenced aspirations	Would you say that this has influenced your preferences with regards to (not) living		if d24_press_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module e: Migration history & awareness				
e1_invimmpast_d	Failed migration preparation (past 5 years)	In the past five years, have you ever prepared to go and live outside of West africa, but not been able to go?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e2_intemigrate_d	Knows internal migrant	And, do you know anyone who used to live here who has moved to another part of Senegal during the past five		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e3_wafmigrate_d	Knows international (within WA) migrant	Do you know anyone who used to live here who has moved to another country in West-Africa during the past five years?		if e2_intemigrate_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e4_wafmigrateten_d	Knows more than 10 international (within WA) migrants	Would you say that you know more than ten people from here who have moved to another country in West-Africa during the past five years?		if e3_wafmigrate_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

e5_extemigrate_d	Knows international (outside WA) migrant	Do you know anyone who used to live here who has moved outside of West-Africa during the past five years?		if e2_intemigrate_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e6_extemigrateten_d	Knows more than 10 international (outside WA) migrants	Would you say that you know more than ten people from here who have moved to another country outside of West-Africa during the past five		if e6_extemigrateten_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e7_injured_d	Has been injured, detained or stuck in a country	In the past 5 years, have you been injured, detained or stuck in a country whilst on the way to move to another country?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e8_deported_d	Has been deported and forced to go back to Senegal	Have you been deported from abroad and forced to come back to Senegal?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e9_failother_d	Knows of other's failed migration experiences	Did anybody you know have any of these experiences or passed away on their way to		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e10_miginreq_d	Knows requirements to migrate outside of WA	Are you familiar with all the requirements to live legally with a visa for an extended period of time outside of West		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e11_migagency_d	Knows migration agency	Do you know any agency or company that could arrange your permit and travel to go		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	

		Refuse to answer	.b	
e12_migreg2_d	Thinks that meets all requirements to migrate to preferred destination	And, do you think you could meet the requirements to travel legally to live in your preferred destination?		if e10_miginreq_d=1 & d3_migpref_c2=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e13_pass_d	Has had a passport	Have you ever had a passport?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e14_passnow_d	Has valid passport	Do you have a valid passport now?		e13_pass_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e15_visa_d	Has applied for visa	Have you ever applied for a visa for another country?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e16_visanum_n	Number of times applied for visa	How many times have you ever applied?		
e17_visayes_d	Has gotten a visa	Have you ever succeeded in getting a visa?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e18_otherpath_d	Knows of irregular means to migrate	And, do you know how to make the necessary arrangements to go and live in another country without a visa and passport?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e19_otherpathcons_d	Would consider irregular means to migrate	And, would you consider going about it this way?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

e20_miginf_d	<i>Has been exposed to mig. inf. cmpgn. (last year)</i>	In the past year, have you encountered any advertisements or event-related information about international migration, specifically regarding people moving between countries, in		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e21_miginfch_c6	<i>Channels where heard/seen mig. inf. cmpgn.</i>	Where did you see or hear this information?		
		TV	1	
		Radio	2	
		Social media / internet	3	
		Event / workshop	4	
		Poster	5	
		Other	6	
		Don't remember	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e22_miginfmes_c6	<i>Message of mig. inf. cmpgn.</i>	Do you remember what the campaign or campaigns were telling you to do or not do?		
		Telling people to migrate	1	
		Telling people how to migrate	2	
		Telling people not to migrate	3	
		Welcoming immigrants from other countries	4	
		Warning people about dangers of smuggling / migrating irregularly (without papers)	5	
		Other	6	
		Don't remember	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e23_miginfeff_c3	<i>Influence of mig. inf. cmpgn.</i>	How did these campaigns influence your view about migrating?		
		Now, you prefer less to migrate	1	
		They did not have an influence	2	
		Now, yo prefer more to migrate	3	
		Don't remember	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e24a_mcfinsen_d e25a_mcfinwa_d e26a_mcfinaf_d e27a_mcfinoaf_d	<i>Thinks has the financial means to travel ...</i>	In the following section, I will ask you several questions related to the possibility of going to a place outside of your city/village to live . Please only provide YES or NO answers to these questions. Do you think you have the financial means to cover the costs of this journey?		
		No	0	

		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e24b_mcfinyrsen_d e25b_mcfinyrwa_d e26b_mcfinyraf_d e27b_mcfinyroaf_d	Thinks can get the financial means to travel ... within a year	Would you be able to get the financial means within a year?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e24c_mcphysen_d e25c_mcphywa_d e26c_mcphyaf_d e27c_mcphyoaf_d	Does not have any physical impairment that would difficult a	Do you have any physical impairment that would make this travel really difficult?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e24d_mcfamsen_d e25d_mcfamwa_d e26d_mcfamaf_d e27d_mcfamoaf_d	Thinks family will support a decision to move ...	If you were to decide to move somewhere else, do you think your family will support your decision to move to...		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
e25e_mclegwa_d e26e_mclegaf_d e27e_mclegoaf_d	Thinks has the legal means to travel ...	Do you think you could get a passport and a visa to move and live legally outside of		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module f: Involuntary Immobility				
f1_happy_c3	Thinks life is good in [LOCATION]	Is life good here in [LOCATION]?:		
		No, life is not good here	1	
		Neither good, neither bad	2	
		Yes, life is good here	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f2_opportunities_d	Thinks that there are good opportunities in	Are there good opportunities for you here in [LOCATION]?:		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f3_invts_d	Has made significant financial investments in [LOCATION]	Have you made significant financial investments here in [LOCATION]. (For example; a house, a car, or a business?)		

		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f4_invimmm_d	Feels cannot leave [LOCATION] to go and live in another country	Do you feel that you cannot leave [LOCATION] to go and live in another country?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f5_invimmmoutcon_d	Feels cannot leave [LOCATION] because of things outside of their	And, do you feel you cannot leave because of things outside of your control?		if f4_invimmmperl oc_d=1
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f6_invimmmrankX_c8		You have mentioned that there are things outside of your control impacting your ability to move abroad. Please rank the following factors from the most constraining to the least constraining in your opinion. If there are factors not listed in the provided answers, please use the category 'other'.		if f5_invimmmout con_d=1
		Legal restrictions like not being able to get a visa	1	
		Financial constraints like not having money to pay for the journey	2	
		Security issues here or in the place I would like to move	3	
		Lack of information	4	
		Parents dont allow me to leave	5	
		Other family responsibilities	6	
		Health problems	7	
		Other	8	
f7_invimmmrankoth_t	Other factors	Please specify		if f6_invimmmrankX_c8=8
		Open answer	s	
f8_invimmsen_d	Feels cannot move to other villages/ cities in Senegal	Do you feel that you cannot move to other villages or cities in Senegal?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

f9_invimmiwa_d	Feels cannot move to another country within WA	Do you feel that you cannot move to another country within West Africa.		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f10_invimmowa_d	Feels cannot move to another country outside WA	And do you feel that you cannot move to another country outside of West Africa?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f11_invimmoaf_d	Feels cannot move to another country outside Africa	Do you feel that you cannot move to another country outside of Africa?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f12_invimmfeel_c5	Feelings about Involuntary Immobility	You mentioned you think you are unable to leave [LOCATION]. How do you feel about this?		if f8_invimmsen_d OR f9_invimmiwa_d OR f10_invimmowa_d OR f11_invimmoaf_d=1
		I feel very frustrated by this, I don't see many opportunities for me in the future	0	
		I feel somehow frustrated by	1	
		I don't have a strong feeling about it	2	
		I feel good about it, it does not affect my daily life	3	
		I feel good about it, I know that if I want I will move outside africa eventuallv	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
f13_invimmfam_c3	Current inability to go live abroad is causing you problems with family	Is your current inability to go live abroad causing you problems with your family?		if invimmsen OR invimmiwa OR invimmowa OR
		Not at all	1	
		Somewhat	2	
		Very much	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

f14_invimmeff_d	<i>Life goals have changed due to immobility</i>	Before you mentioned that you feel that you cannot realize your life goals here. You have also mentioned that you cannot leave [LOCATION] either. Do you think your life goals will change because of this?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module g: Alternatives to migration				
g1_localopp_d	<i>Has explored local opp. to achieve local goals</i>	You mentioned that it is more feasible to achieve your main life goals outside of [LOCATION]. Have you already explored other ways to achieve these life goals here that would not require you to move?"		if b5_firstlgw here_c3=1 or 2 or 3 or b6_secondlgw here_c3=1 or 2 or 3
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
g2_localsteps_ms	*	What have you done to achieve your life goals in [LOCATION]?		if g1_localopp_d
		Seek education in [LOCATION]	1	
		Seek training opportunities in [LOCATION]	2	
		Find employment in [LOCATION]	3	
		Change employment in [LOCATION]	4	
		Improve my social network in [LOCATION]	5	
		Invest in my own business in [LOCATION]	6	
		Shape change in [LOCATION]	7	
		Other	8	
g3_localstepsoth_t	<i>Other things done in [LOCATION]</i>	Please specify		local_steps= 8
		Open answer	s	
g4_othlocalopp_d	<i>Knows of other useful opportunities but has not used them</i>	Are there any opportunities here you are aware of and that might help you achieve your goals but you haven't made use		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
g5_othlocaloppno_c 4	*	And why haven't you taken advantage of these opportunities yet?		if othlocalopp=0
		My future is not here	0	
		No time	1	
		No energy	2	

		Family obligations	3	
		Lack of financial means	4	
		Other reason	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module h: Livelihoods and opportunities				
h1_wrk_c9	Main occupation	Now, we will talk about your main occupation. Your main occupation is the activity that you spend most of your time on. It can be paid or unpaid. Which is your current main		
		Employed and receiving a weekly or monthly salary	1	
		Day labourer/ Seasonal worker / Casual work	2	
		Farming, fishing, or rearing animals	3	
		Working on own account or business	4	
		Studying/Training	5	
		Unemployed	6	
		Not working because of long-term sickness or disability	7	
		Doing unpaid housework, looking after children or other	8	
		Other, please specify	9	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
h2_wrkoth_t	Other main occupation	Please specify		
		Open answer	s	
h3_wrktype_c12	Occupation's sector	And, which kind of activity best describes this main work situation?		if h1_wrk_c9=1 or 2 or 3 or 4
		Agriculture / Farming / Fishing / Forestry	1	
		Trader / Hawker / Vendor	2	
		Retail / Shop	3	
		Unskilled manual worker (e.g. cleaner, laborer, domestic help, unskilled manufacturing	4	
		worker, unskilled construction Artisan or skilled manual		
		worker (e.g. electrician, mechanic, machinist, skilled	5	
		manufacturing worker, skilled construction worker)		
		Clerical or secretarial	6	
		Supervisor / Foreman / Senior manager	7	
		Security services (police, army, private security)	8	
		Mid-level professional (e.g. teacher, nurse, mid-level	9	
		government officer)		

		Upper-level professional (e.g. banker, doctor, lawyer, engineer, accountant, professor, senior level	10	
		Transport (taxi, moto, etc...)	11	
		Not sure how to classify	12	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
h4_wrktypewage_c4	Type of wages received	In this job, do you receive a salary or are you self-employed?		if h1_wrk_c9=1 or 2 or 3 or 4
		Receives a salary	1	
		Is self-employed	2	
		Does not receive a salary	3	
		Not sure how to classify	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
h5_wrksrch_d	Is actively looking for a (new,	Are you actively looking for a (new, another) job?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
h6_goodjob_c5	Easiness to find a good job in [LOCATION]	In a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents "Very difficult" and 5 " Very easy", how easy is it to find a good job in [LOCATION]? Would you say that it is...		
		Very easy	1	
		Easy	2	
		Neutral	3	
		Difficult	4	
		Very difficult	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
h07_livinf_d	Exposed to livelihoods inf. cmpgn.	In the past year, have you encountered any advertisements or event-related information about working opportunities in		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
h08_livinfch_c6	Channels where heard/seen livelihoods inf. cmpgn.	Where did you see or hear this information?		if h07_livinf_d =1
		TV	1	
		Radio	2	
		Social media / internet	3	
		Event / workshop	4	
		Poster	5	

		Other	6	
		Don't remember	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
ho9_livinfmts_c6	Message of livelihoods inf. cmpgn.	Do you remember what the campaign or campaigns were telling?		if ho7_livinfmts_d =1
		About work opportunities in Ziguinchor city	1	
		About work opportunities in Ziguinchor commune	2	
		About work opportunities in Kolda city	3	
		About work opportunities in Kolda commune	4	
		About work opportunities in Bagadadji commune	5	
		About work opportunities in Dakar	6	
		About work opportunities in Senegal (NOT DAKAR NOT ZIGUINCHOR, NOT KOLDA, NOTY BAGADADJI)	7	
		Other	8	
		Don't remember	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module i: Cognitive decision-making and biases				
i1_informdeclife_d // i1_informdecmig_d	Life/migration decision: fully informed before I make a decision	We would like to know how you take general life decisions. We also would like to know how would you take decisions related to migration. For this, we will read several statements and we want you to say whether these are "false" (1), "sometimes true, but it depends on the situation" (2) or "true" (3). I am fully informed		
		False	1	
		Sometimes	2	
		True	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i2_rightdeclife_d // i2_rightdecmig_d	Life/migration decision: does what feels right	When I make a decision, I do what feels right	2	
		False	1	
		Sometimes	2	
		True	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i3_peopleddeclife_d // i3_peopleddecmig_d	Life/migration decision: often asks other people for	When I make an important decision, I often ask other people to help me	3	
		False	1	
		Sometimes	2	

		True	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i4_avoiddeclife_d // i4_avoiddecmig_d	Life/migration decision: tries to avoid making decisions	I don't like making decisions, so I try to avoid it	4	
		False	1	
		Sometimes	2	
		True	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i5_quickdeclife_d // i5_quickdecmig_d	Life/migration decision: makes decisions quickly	I make decisions quickly	5	
		False	1	
		Sometimes	2	
		True	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i6_skillfull_c3	Can handle difficult situations	Can you handle difficult situations?		
		No	1	
		Somewhat	2	
		Yes	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i7_notleaveunc_c3	Family and friends prevents them from leaving	Do your ties with families and friends prevent you from moving?		
		No	1	
		Somewhat	2	
		Yes	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i8_notleaveinv_c5	Agreement: I wouldn't want to leave because I have put a lot into this place	Now I would like to know your level of agreement with respect to two statements. Please tell me if you strongly disagree, disagree, neither disagree or agree, agree or strongly agree. First statement is: "I wouldn't want to leave because I have put a lot into this place"		
		Strongly disagree	1	
		Disagree	2	
		Neither agree, nor disagree	3	
		Agree	4	
		Strongly agree	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

i9_notleavefear_c5	Agreement: If I moved abroad, I fear it might not be the right decision	And second statement is "If I moved abroad, I fear it might not be the right decision"		
		Strongly disagree	1	
		Disagree	2	
		Neither agree, nor disagree	3	
		Agree	4	
		Strongly agree	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i10_changeaverse_c10	Willingness a to make significant changes in life	And, on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means 'not willing at all' and 10 means 'extremely willing,' how willing are you to make significant changes in		
		Not at all	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Very much	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i11_comties_c10	Level of attachment to [LOCATION]	On a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means 'not attached at all' and 10 means 'extremely attached,' how attached are		
		Not at all	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Very much	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i12_attachment_c3	Reasons for attachment	Is this attachment based on		if i11_comties_c10 > 1
		Emotional ties	1	

		Practical reasons (e.g., a job, responsibilities)	2	
		Both, emotional and practical reasons	3	
		Other	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
i13_fiveopp_c6	Five opportunities choice	Finally, imagine that you were offered the five opportunities below and that you could only choose one. Which one would you choose, or would you choose none?		
		A permanent job with an average senegalese salary	1	
		The opportunity and financial support for additional	2	
		The necessary money to start a small business	3	
		A plane ticket and a granted visa to move elsewhere in	4	
		A plane ticket and a granted visa to move elsewhere outside	5	
		None of the above	6	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module j: Household economic wellbeing				
j1_hhhead_d	Is the head of the household	Are you a (the) head of the household?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j2_hhhd_XXX_d	*	Whats your relationship with the head of the household?		if j1_hhhead_d=
		Spouse/partner	1	
		Ex-spouse/ex-partner	2	
		Son/daughter	3	
		Father/mother	4	
		Brother/sister	5	
		Cousin	6	
		Other relatives	7	
		Other non-relative	8	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j3_hhcont_c4	Personal contribution to hh expenses	With respect to your household's expenses. How much do you personally contribute to covering		
		None of them	1	
		Less than half of them	2	
		Half or more than half of them	3	
		All of them	4	

		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j4_hhinc_c8	Hh's most important source of income	If you think about your household's income, would you say that the most important source of income is... (Please note that household income refers to the sum of all the entries of money that contribute to the common pot)		
		Income from wages from household members	1	
		Income from agriculture, fishing, or herding	2	
		Income from family business / household members business	3	
		Income from renting out property	4	
		Money received from people living abroad	5	
		Money received from people living elsewhere in Senegal	6	
		Support or aid from the authorities or other	7	
		Other	8	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j5_hhsit_c3	Hh's financial situation	Thinking about your household's current financial situation, would you say your household is ... (READ		
		Finding it difficult to get by	1	
		Coping	2	
		Living comfortably	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j6_hunger_d	Has gone to sleep without having had enough food to eat that day (over the past	Over the past month, have you gone to sleep without having had enough food to eat that day?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j7_emrg_d	Would be able to get 30,000 CFA within a week for emergency	If you needed 30,000 senegalese francs for an emergency, would you be able to get it within a week?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

j8_relwealth_c10	Perceived relative living standards	Think about the difference between rich and poor households in [LOCATION], if 0 represents the very poorest households and 10 represents the very richest households. Where would you place your own household?		
		Poorest households	0	
		1	1	
		2	2	
		3	3	
		4	4	
		5	5	
		6	6	
		7	7	
		8	8	
		9	9	
		Richest households	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j9_XXX_d	*	I am going to list different things that people might have in their houses. Please tell me if your household has any of them, in working condition.		
		Chair	1	
		Table	2	
		Sofa	3	
		Bed	4	
		Television	5	
		Refrigerator or freezer	6	
		Gas or electric stove	7	
		Washing machine	8	
		Electric fan	9	
		Air conditioning	10	
		Computer or laptop	11	
		Motorcycle	12	
		Car	13	
j10_roomnum_n	Number of rooms in the hh	And how many rooms are in your house? Count only bedrooms, living rooms and dining rooms, not kitchen, bathroom, and storage rooms.		
		Open answer	#	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j11_water_d	Hh has piped water	Do you have piped water?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	

		Refuse to answer	.b	
j12_toilet_c4	Type of toilet in the hh	And which kind of toilet do you have?		
		Toilet flushed directly with water from a pipe	1	
		Toilet flushed with water from a bucket	2	
		Latrine (not flushed with water)	3	
		No toilet at home	4	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j13_floor_c7	Main type of floor material	What material is the floor in most of the house made of?		
		Concrete or cement	1	
		Tiles, brick, granite, stone	2	
		Wood	3	
		Vinyl	4	
		Dirt, sand, dung	5	
		Cane	6	
		Other	7	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j14_houseown_d	Respondent or family owns the	Do you or your family own this house?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j15_landown_d	Respondent or family owns land	Do you or your family own any land?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j16_phnuse_d	Uses mobile phone	Do you use a mobile phone?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j17_phntype_d		Is it a smartphone, touchphone, or a tablet?		if j16_phnuse_d
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j18_phnshr_c2		Are you sharing it with someone else, or are you the only adult using it?		if j16_phnuse_d =1
		Sharing it with someone else	0	
		The only adult using it	1	
		Don't know	.a	

		Refuse to answer	.b	
j19_phncred_c3	Frequency of credit to make calls	Do you have credit to make calls always, sometimes, or		if j16_phnuse_d
		Always	1	
		Sometimes	2	
		Rarely or never	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j20_phndata_c3	Frequency of mobile data	Do you have mobile data always, sometimes, or rarely?		if j16_phnuse_d
		Always	1	
		Sometimes	2	
		Rarely or never	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j21_some_c7	Social media use	How often do you check social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok or similar?		if j16_phnuse_d =1
		Every hour	1	
		Every day	2	
		Every two days	3	
		Every week	4	
		Every two weeks	5	
		Every month	6	
		Rarely or never	7	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j22_drought_d	Hh has been affected by drought in the last two years	I am now going to ask about environmental problems in Casamance which you may have experienced. In the last two years, has your household been affected by any droughts?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j23_flood_d	Hh has been affected by flood in the last two years	Has it been affected by floods?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j24_temp_d	Hh has been affected by temp. increase in the last	Has it been affected by a clear temperature increase or heatwaves?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	

j25_soil_d	<i>Hh has been affected by soil salinization in the</i>	Has it been affected by soil salinization?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j26_defor_d	<i>Hh has been affected by deforestation in the</i>	Has it been affected by deforestation?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
j27_envimp_c3	<i>Impact of env. issues on hh's livelihood or income</i>	How far have these problems affected your household's livelihood or income?		if rainfall=1 OR flood=1 OR temp=1 OR soil=1
		Not at all	1	
		Somewhat	2	
		Very much	2	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Module k: Education and religion				
k1_edu_c10	<i>Highest level of formal education obtained</i>	What is the highest level of formal education that you have completed?		
		None/no formal education	1	
		Religious schooling only	2	
		Primary school (started without completing)	3	
		Primary school (completed)	4	
		Lower/junior secondary	5	
		Upper/senior secondary	6	
		Tertiary (Bachelors)	7	
		Tertiary (Masters)	8	
		Tertiary (PhD)	9	
		Other, please specify	10	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
k2_eduoth_t	<i>Other level of highest education</i>	Please specify		
		Open answer	s	
k3_edunow_c7	<i>Is currently studying or taking classes for a</i>	Are you currently studying or taking classes for a diploma or degree?		
		No	1	
		Yes, secondary school	2	
		Yes, diploma from trade school or vocational training	3	
		Yes, bachelor's degree	4	
		Yes, master's degree	5	

		Yes, PhD degree	6	
		Yes, other	7	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
k4_voc_d	Has participated in a vocational/skills training	Have you participated in any vocational or skills training course?		
		No	0	
		Yes	1	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
k5_voctype_c7	Type of vocational/skills training	Which type of vocational training?		if k4_voc_d=1
		Automotive repair	1	
		Plumbing	2	
		Culinary arts	3	
		Graphic design	4	
		Fashion design	5	
		Welding	6	
		Other, please specify	7	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
k6_voctypeoth_t	Other vocational/skills training	Please specify		
		Open answer	s	
k7_eth_c17	Ethnic group	Which of these best describes your ethnic group?		
		Wolof	1	
		Fula	2	
		Serer	3	
		Jola	4	
		Bainuk	5	
		Balanta	6	
		Manjack	7	
		Mankanya	8	
		Karoninka	9	
		Bandial	10	
		Mandinka	11	
		Soninke	12	
		Other, please specify	13	
k8_ethoth_t	Other ethnic group	Please specify		if k7_eth_c13=13
		Open answer	s	
k9_rlg_c9	Religion	What is your religion?		
		Muslim	1	
		Muslim - Xaadir (Qādiriyya) Sufi order	2	
		Muslim - Tijaniyyah order	3	
		Muslim - Mourides order	4	

		Muslim - Layene Sufi order	5	
		Christian – Catholic	6	
		Christian – Protestant	7	
		Christian – Other	8	
		Other, please specify	9	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
k10_rlgoth_t	Other religion	Other religion		if rlg=8
		Open answer	#	
k11_relimp_c3	Importance of religion in life	And, how important would you say religion is in your life? (Enumerator hint: Would you say that it is very important in your life, somewhat important, or not so important?)		
		Very important	1	
		Somewhat important	2	
		Not so important	3	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
k12_relpred_c5	Thinks that future is in God's hands	On a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 indicates "Strongly Disagree" and 5 indicates "Strongly Agree," please indicate your belief regarding the notion that one's future is in God's hands.		
		Strongly Disagree	1	
		Disagree	2	
		Neutral	3	
		Agree	4	
		Strongly Agree	5	
		Don't know	.a	
		Refuse to answer	.b	
Post interview module				
post_available_n	Would be available for future contact	Thank you. That was the end of the interview. Would be available for future contact		
post_impatient_d	Respondent was impatient	Respondent was impatient		
post_otherpresence_d	Someone else was present during interview	Someone else was present during interview		
post_otherinfluence_d	Someone influenced Respondent made	Someone influenced interview responses		
post_uncomfortable_d	enumerator feel uncomfortable doing interview	Respondent made enumerator feel uncomfortable doing interview		
post_problem_d	There was a problem during the	There was a problem during the interview		
post_attitude_c4	Respondents attitude	Respondents attitude		
post_enjoyed_d	Respondent enjoyed the	Respondent enjoyed the interview		

gps_lat_n	<i>Location: latitude</i>	Location: latitude		
gps_lon_n	<i>Location: longitude</i>	Location: longitude		
gps_alt_n	<i>Location: altitude</i>	Location: altitude		
gps_acc_n	<i>Location: accuracy</i>	Location: accuracy		
post_durations_n	<i>Duration of interview in sec</i>	Duration of interview in sec		
post_tssize_n	<i># of adults aged 18-39 living in the hh</i>	# of adults aged 18-39 living in the hh		
		Identification of respondent		
id_respondent_t	<i>Respondent key identifier</i>	Respondent key identifier		
id_uniqueid_t	<i>Unique interview identifier</i>	Unique interview identifier		
id_name_t	<i>Name of respondent</i>	Name of respondent		
id_contact_n	<i>Phone number for future contact</i>	Phone number for future contact		
id_hhheadname_t	<i>Name of head of the household</i>	Name of head of the household		
id_hhheadphone_n	<i>Phone of head of the household</i>	Phone of head of the household		
id_othname_t	<i>Other person's name for future contact</i>	Other person's name for future contact		
id_othphone_n	<i>Other person's phone for future contact</i>	Other person's phone for future contact		
id_fb_t	<i>Respondent's facebook id</i>	Respondent's facebook id		
id_wavenum_n	<i>Respondent's wave number</i>	Respondent's wave number		